

The tug-of-war between sports and physical activity anxiety in quest for self-actualization among university students

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relationship between sports and physical activity anxiety and self-actualization among university students. Utilizing a quantitative research design with a descriptive correlation approach, the study involved 2,043 respondents selected through simple random sampling. Two primary instruments were employed: the physical activity and sport anxiety scale (PASAS) to measure anxiety levels and the index of self-actualization to assess self-actualization traits. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Spearman's rho correlation coefficient to explore the relationships between the variables. Results revealed that respondents exhibited low levels of sports and physical activity anxiety and moderate levels of self-actualization. Notably, a significant negative correlation was identified between sports and physical activity anxiety and self-actualization. These findings imply that higher anxiety related to sports and physical activities is associated with lower levels of self-actualization, highlighting the need for supportive environments that mitigate anxiety in physical activity contexts. The study underscores the importance of implementing strategies to reduce anxiety and promote self-discovery, ultimately fostering resilience and personal growth among students.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Self-actualization, as conceptualized in humanistic psychology, particularly by Abraham Maslow, represents the highest level of psychological development where an individual seeks to actualize their inherent potential and fulfill their unique capabilities [1]. This concept, positioned at the peak of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, transcends basic physical and psychological requirements, focusing instead on the realization of personal growth, creativity, and the pursuit of meaning [2]. Self-actualization involves striving for authenticity and congruence between one's actions and intrinsic values, as individuals progressively align their behaviors with a true sense of self [3]. Central to self-actualization are characteristics such as autonomy, resilience, self-awareness, and an acceptance of both strengths and limitations. Self-actualized individuals often demonstrate

high levels of empathy, openness to experience, and a profound appreciation for life, leading them to form deep, meaningful relationships and contribute positively to their communities [4]. In educational settings, particularly among university students, self-actualization can manifest as an intrinsic drive toward learning, personal development, and a proactive orientation toward challenges and self-improvement [5].

Sports and physical anxiety are a type of situational anxiety that arises in contexts involving physical performance, athletic activities, or physical education. It is often marked by increased stress, fear of judgment, and worries about physical competence. This anxiety can stem from various factors, including self-comparison, negative past experiences, perceived social pressures, and fear of failure, all of which may trigger psychological responses like nervousness, self-doubt, and even avoidance behaviors [6]. Students who experience high levels of sports anxiety may show reluctance or even refuse to engage in activities, which can hinder their physical development, reduce social interactions, and limit opportunities to build teamwork and leadership skills [7]. Further, this anxiety may negatively affect their overall academic experience, as the stress linked to physical performance can spill over into other areas of school life, impacting focus, motivation, and confidence [8]. By recognizing the effects of sports and physical anxiety, educators and program developers can better support students in overcoming these challenges and foster an environment that promotes both physical health and psychological well-being [9].

Today's students face a range of challenges in achieving self-actualization, often compounded by sports and physical activity anxiety, both of which can hinder their personal growth and academic performance. In an educational climate that increasingly emphasizes academic success, students frequently feel pressure to excel, leaving little room to pursue self-fulfillment or explore their potential beyond structured expectations [10]. This pressure, combined with the fear of failure and social comparison, can lead to heightened sports and physical activity anxiety, as students worry about their physical abilities and perceived competence in competitive or performance-driven contexts [11]. Physical education settings can exacerbate this anxiety, as students often feel self-conscious or fear judgment from peers, particularly if they perceive themselves as less skilled [12]. This anxiety frequently manifests in avoidance behaviors, such as reluctance to participate in group sports or physical activities, which in turn limits their opportunities to develop confidence, resilience, and teamwork skills essential for self-actualization [13].

Research on students' self-actualization has underscored the importance of personal growth and fulfillment in academic settings, examining factors that support or inhibit this developmental process. Self-actualization, often linked to psychological well-being and motivation, is a significant predictor of academic success and life satisfaction among students [14]. Studies by Maunz and Glaser [15] indicates that self-actualization is facilitated by environments that encourage autonomy, mastery, and meaningful engagement. In a study examining self-actualization among university students, Polat *et al.* [16] found that students with higher levels of autonomy and self-efficacy tend to experience greater satisfaction with academic life and report lower stress levels. Similarly, research by Gopinath [17] highlighted that supportive educational climate that offer growth opportunities—through extracurricular activities, open discussions, and mentorship—can significantly enhance students' self-perception and drive toward self-actualization. Additionally, the study by Viterouli *et al.* [18] demonstrated that students who engage in self-reflective practices and set personal goals show a stronger orientation toward self-actualization, with noticeable improvements in resilience and academic performance. However, barriers to self-actualization, such as high-performance pressure and limited opportunities for creative expression, often lead to decreased motivation and increased stress among students, as noted by studies on educational burnout [19].

Research on sports and physical activity anxiety outside of student populations has examined a diverse range of demographics, uncovering complex psychological and physiological impacts. Studies on professional athletes, for instance, reveal that performance anxiety—commonly known as “choking under pressure”—is a widespread phenomenon that affects both individual and team performance. Mahamid and Bert [20] found that this anxiety often stems from fear of negative evaluation, perfectionism, and high expectations, which can disrupt concentration and motor skills, ultimately hindering performance outcomes. Among amateur athletes and fitness enthusiasts, sports and physical activity anxiety is frequently linked to self-esteem and body image concerns [21]. For example, Özyol [22] demonstrated that amateur athletes who experience social physique anxiety—fear over how others perceive their appearance—tend to avoid physical activities, which can negatively impact their health and well-being. Additionally, research on clinical populations has shown that individuals with anxiety disorders may experience heightened physical activity anxiety due to symptoms like increased heart rate, which they might misinterpret as signs of panic [23].

Despite extensive research on sports and physical activity anxiety, its specific link to self-actualization among university students remains largely unexplored. While studies highlight anxiety's effects on performance and self-esteem, few examine its impact on students' personal growth. Given the unique challenges of university life and rising mental health concerns, understanding this relationship is crucial. This study fills a critical gap by offering insights that can inform educational and mental health interventions to

support student well-being and self-actualization. This research generally aimed to provide answer on what is the relationship of sports and physical activity anxiety on the self-actualization of university students?

The novelty of this research lies in its integrated exploration of sports and physical activity anxiety and self-actualization among university students—an area largely unexplored in existing literature. Unlike previous studies that examine these factors separately, this study highlights their interconnected impact on student well-being and personal growth. By addressing this gap, it offers fresh insights into psychological barriers to self-actualization, informing targeted interventions in education, mental health, and sports engagement. The findings contribute to educational psychology and sports science, emphasizing the need for supportive environments that foster resilience, self-awareness, and a positive relationship with physical activity. Ultimately, this research aids educators and policymakers in creating holistic frameworks that enhance students' academic experiences and overall well-being.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design

This study utilized a quantitative research design, specifically employing a descriptive-correlational approach to examine the relationship between sports and physical activity anxiety and self-actualization among university students. Quantitative research design is a systematic investigation that focuses on quantifying data and applying statistical, mathematical, or computational techniques to analyze relationships between variables [24]. On the other hand, the descriptive-correlational design is a type of quantitative approach used to identify and describe associations between variables without manipulating them, allowing for the examination of naturally occurring relationships [25]. The quantitative research design, specifically the descriptive-correlational approach, was selected for this study due to its suitability for examining the association between sports and physical activity anxiety and self-actualization. This approach enables the researcher to measure the degree and direction of the relationship between the two variables in a structured, objective manner, providing insights that can be generalized to the wider student population [26].

2.2. Respondents and sampling

This study utilized a simple random sampling technique to select 2,043 university students, ensuring that each had an equal chance of inclusion and minimizing sampling bias. Simple random sampling, a probability-based method, is effective for generating representative and unbiased samples, making it ideal for examining relationships between variables in large populations [27]. Given the study's focus on sports and physical activity anxiety in relation to self-actualization, this approach provided a diverse and representative dataset. The robust sample size allowed for reliable statistical analyses and generalizable findings, enhancing the study's validity and ensuring that the results accurately reflect the broader student population.

2.3. Research instrument

This study utilized two primary instruments to measure sports and physical activity anxiety as well as self-actualization among university students. The physical activity and sport anxiety scale (PASAS), developed by Carter *et al.* [28] was employed to assess students' levels of anxiety related to sports and physical activities. PASAS specifically gauges anxiety triggered by various factors in physical activity settings, such as performance pressure, social interactions, and self-perceptions of physical capability. With a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.86, PASAS demonstrates high internal consistency, establishing it as a reliable tool for evaluating sports and physical activity anxiety across diverse populations and contexts.

Additionally, this study employed the short index of self-actualization developed by Kaufman [14] which measures the extent to which individuals display characteristics of self-actualization, such as self-awareness, authenticity, creativity, and the pursuit of personal growth. With a Cronbach's alpha of 0.72, this scale also shows strong internal consistency, ensuring reliable measurement of self-actualizing behaviors. Respondents rate their agreement with statements that reflect traits of self-actualization, providing insights into their psychological development and alignment with self-actualizing qualities.

2.4. Statistical analysis

This study utilized descriptive statistics, including mean and composite mean, to summarize and describe the respondents' levels of sports and physical activity anxiety and self-actualization. The mean provides an average score representing the central tendency of the data, while the composite mean offers an overall measure by aggregating the means of individual items within each variable. To examine the relationship between sports and physical activity anxiety and self-actualization, Spearman's rho correlation coefficient was used.

Spearman's rho is a non-parametric measure of rank correlation that assesses the strength and direction of the relationship between two variables [29]. This method is advantageous when working with ordinal data or when data do not meet the assumptions of normality, as it does not require a normal distribution [30]. Spearman's rho was selected for this study to effectively capture the degree of monotonic relationship between sports and physical activity anxiety and self-actualization among university students.

3. RESULTS

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for sports and physical activity anxiety levels among the respondents. This table summarizes the overall anxiety scores, including subdimensions related to performance pressure, social interactions, and self-perceptions in physical activity settings. This offers a detailed view of the respondents' anxiety experiences in sports and physical activity contexts.

Table 2 displays the descriptive statistics for the self-actualization levels of the respondents. The data includes mean scores across various self-actualizing behaviors, such as self-awareness, authenticity, and personal growth. This provides insights into the degree to which respondents exhibit characteristics associated with self-actualization.

Table 1. Sports and physical activity anxiety among the respondents

Statements	Weighted mean	Verbal description
1. I feel nervous if other people watch me when I am exercising/working out.	2.60	Agree
2. I usually get nervous when I play sports in front of even a few people watching.	2.56	Agree
3. I am afraid that people will find fault with my performance while playing sports.	2.54	Agree
4. Sometimes I think I am too concerned with what other people think about my performance while exercising/working out.	2.51	Agree
5. I feel self-conscious when playing sports.	2.43	Disagree
6. I worry about what people will think of me while playing sports, even though it will not make any difference.	2.39	Disagree
7. I am usually worried about what kind of impression I make while playing sports.	2.37	Disagree
8. I pass the ball to a teammate when I get nervous.	2.34	Disagree
9. I rarely worry about what kind of impression I am making on someone while exercising/working out.	2.28	Disagree
10. I avoid exercising/working out where others can see me.	2.26	Disagree
11. Other people's opinions of how well I play sports do not bother me.	2.25	Disagree
12. I could not care less if an audience was watching me perform.	2.18	Disagree
13. I feel that I will humiliate myself when I play sports.	2.16	Disagree
14. I feel I will humiliate myself when I exercise/work out.	2.15	Disagree
15. I avoid social gatherings if I think they will involve an athletic activity.	2.10	Disagree
16. I do not want the ball to come to me when I play team sports.	2.09	Disagree
Overall mean	2.33	Low sports and physical activity anxiety

Legend: 4.00–3.50=Strongly agree (High sports and physical activity anxiety)
 3.49–2.50=Agree (Moderate sports and physical activity anxiety)
 2.49–1.50=Disagree (Low sports and physical activity anxiety)
 1.49–1.00=Strongly disagree (No sports and physical activity anxiety)

Table 2. Self-actualization of the generation Z students

Statements	Weighted mean	Verbal description
10. It is better to be yourself than to be popular.	3.41	Agree
8. I fear failure.	3.07	Agree
15. I am loved because I give love.	3.02	Agree
14. I am bothered by fears of being inadequate.	2.77	Agree
7. I can like people without having to approve of them.	2.73	Agree
12. I can express my feelings even when they may result in undesirable consequences.	2.56	Agree
2. I feel I must do what others expect of me.	2.55	Agree
1. I do not feel ashamed of any of my emotions.	2.53	Agree
4. I feel free to be angry at those I love.	2.48	Disagree
9. I avoid attempts to analyze and simplify complex domains.	2.47	Disagree
5. It is always necessary that others approve what I do.	2.41	Disagree
3. I believe that people are essentially good and can be trusted.	2.37	Disagree
11. I have no mission in life to which I feel especially dedicated.	2.32	Disagree
6. I do not accept my own weaknesses.	2.20	Disagree
13. I do not feel responsible to help anybody.	2.16	Disagree
Composite mean	2.60	Self-actualization is evident

Legend: 4.00–3.50=Strongly agree (Self-actualization is highly evident)
 3.49–2.50=Agree (Self-actualization is evident)
 2.59–1.50=Disagree (Self-actualization is rarely evident)
 1.49–1.00=Strongly disagree (Self-actualization is not evident)

Table 3 presents the results of the statistical test examining the relationship between sports and physical activity anxiety and self-actualization among the respondents. Using Spearman's rho correlation coefficient, this table highlights the strength and direction of the association between these two variables, helping to determine if higher anxiety levels correspond with variations in self-actualization.

Table 3. Test of significant relationship between the respondents' sports and physical anxiety and self-actualization

Paired variables	Spearman Rho correlation coefficient	p-value	Interpretation ($\alpha=0.05$)
Sports and physical anxiety and self-actualization	-.271**	0.000	Significant

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Self-actualization of students

Table 1 presents findings on the self-actualization levels of generation Z students, revealing a composite mean score of 2.60 with a description of "self-actualization is evident." This score suggests that students display notable self-actualizing qualities such as self-awareness, personal growth, and goal orientation. While these traits indicate a commitment to personal development, students may still be in the early to moderate stages of fully achieving their potential. This level of self-actualization implies that respondents are on a path toward authenticity and purpose, though further exploration and growth remain for them to fully realize their potential.

The results suggest that students actively engage in self-discovery and personal development, which can enhance resilience and adaptability. At this stage of self-actualization, students have a clearer sense of identity and purpose, supporting them in making more informed life decisions. However, this evident self-actualization also highlights ongoing growth opportunities, as students could further explore their values and aspirations to maximize their potential. Today's educational environments and societal influences likely play a role in this development. Increased access to information, diverse opportunities, and supportive educational settings encourages personal growth, critical thinking, and self-directed learning, empowering students to pursue self-discovery and identity formation [31], [32]. Social media and global connectivity further expose students to diverse cultures and role models, inspiring them to set meaningful goals aligned with their personal values [33].

Among all statements, "it is better to be yourself than to be popular" had the highest mean score of 3.41, with a description of "agree." This finding underscores a strong student preference for authenticity over external validation, suggesting a commitment to integrity and self-acceptance. Students' emphasis on staying true to themselves highlights a focus on individual strengths and values over societal pressures for popularity, which can bolster confidence and empower them to make value-aligned decisions. Research supports the idea that authenticity strengthens self-actualization, as individuals who remain true to themselves are more likely to pursue personally meaningful goals, fostering fulfillment and a sense of purpose [15], [34]. By embracing authenticity, students are more resilient and committed to their goals, allowing for personal growth and the development of a genuine identity [35].

Conversely, the statement "I do not feel responsible to help anybody" received the lowest mean score of 2.16, with a description of "disagree," suggesting that students generally feel a strong sense of responsibility toward helping others. This response indicates a tendency toward empathy and social responsibility, where assistance to others is viewed not as a burden but as a meaningful contribution to their communities. This sense of unselfishness and connectedness can deepen self-actualization by fostering positive relationships and purpose-driven engagement. Today's youth, exposed to social issues via digital media, often exhibit a heightened sense of responsibility and desire for positive change, engaging in community service, activism, and advocacy [36], [37]. This commitment to helping others reflects a values-driven approach, empowering them as active societal contributors who strive to shape a more equitable future [38].

4.2. Sports and physical activity anxiety of the students

Table 1 presents the levels of sports and physical activity anxiety among the respondents, revealing a composite mean score of 2.33, which is interpreted as "low sports and physical activity anxiety." This indicates that, on average, the respondents experience minimal anxiety in sports and physical activity contexts, suggesting that most students feel relatively at ease when engaging in such activities. A low level of sports and physical anxiety implies that these students may have fewer psychological barriers to participation, which could positively impact their willingness to engage in physical activities and promote a

healthier lifestyle. This result also sets a foundation for understanding how their comfort with physical activities may relate to other aspects of their well-being, such as life satisfaction.

Having low sports and physical activity anxiety among students suggests favorable conditions for promoting active engagement in physical activities without the hindrance of performance-related stress or social discomfort. This low anxiety level may support better participation rates in sports and exercise, which in turn can enhance physical health, mental resilience, and social connection. Furthermore, reduced anxiety in physical activity settings could foster positive attitudes toward lifelong fitness and well-being, as students are less likely to avoid these activities due to fear or self-consciousness. Consequently, low sports and physical anxiety can contribute not only to individual health benefits but also to a more active and engaged student community.

Overcoming sports and physical activity anxiety is crucial for youth as it fosters physical, mental, and social well-being. Reducing anxiety allows young people to engage more confidently in physical activities, which can improve their overall health, boost self-esteem, and build resilience (Ekeland). When they can participate without fear or apprehension, youth are more likely to enjoy the benefits of exercise, including reduced stress, enhanced concentration, and better emotional regulation [39]. Additionally, sports provide an avenue for developing teamwork, leadership, and communication skills [40]. Addressing and overcoming this anxiety empowers young individuals to lead active, balanced lifestyles and cultivates lifelong habits that positively impact their quality of life and social interactions [41].

Further, the statement “I feel nervous if other people watch me when I am exercising/working out” received the highest mean value of 2.60, with a verbal description of “agree.” This indicates that, despite an overall low level of sports and physical activity anxiety, a notable number of respondents still feel self-conscious or uneasy when being observed during physical activities. This suggests that social evaluative anxiety, or the fear of being judged by others, remains a significant factor impacting students’ comfort levels in fitness settings. Such feelings may deter some students from participating fully in group exercises or public workouts, potentially limiting their engagement in beneficial physical activities and pointing to the need for more supportive, judgment-free environments in exercise spaces.

Being judged by others can significantly impact sports and physical activity participation by instilling fear of negative evaluation and leading to heightened anxiety. This fear can deter individuals from trying new activities or participating in sports, as they may worry about their performance, appearance, or skill level in front of peers [42]. Such concerns can create a cycle of avoidance, where the anxiety surrounding judgment reinforces feelings of inadequacy and discourages engagement [43]. Consequently, this can limit opportunities for social interaction, skill development, and the physical and mental health benefits that come from regular participation in sports and physical activities [44].

On the other hand, the statement “I do not want the ball to come to me when I play team sports” received the lowest mean score of 2.09, with a verbal description of “disagree.” This suggests that the majority of respondents do not experience significant anxiety or apprehension when it comes to actively participating in team sports. Their disagreement with this statement indicates a willingness to engage in gameplay and take on roles that require ball handling or involvement, reflecting a level of confidence in their abilities. This positive attitude towards participation in team sports can foster a sense of camaraderie and collaboration among peers, ultimately enhancing both social interaction and overall enjoyment of physical activities. Such findings highlight the importance of encouraging teamwork and skill development in sports, as students who feel more comfortable with participation are likely to experience greater enjoyment and satisfaction in their athletic endeavors.

Many youths today experience less anxiety or apprehension about participating in team sports due to a more supportive and inclusive culture surrounding physical activity [45]. With increased emphasis on teamwork, cooperation, and personal growth over competition, young athletes often feel encouraged to participate regardless of their skill level [46]. Additionally, the rise of social media and digital platforms allows youths to connect and share their experiences, reducing feelings of isolation and judgment. Programs promoting mental health awareness also help normalize discussions about anxiety, equipping young people with coping strategies and fostering a sense of community [47]. Together, these factors create a more positive environment that empowers youths to engage actively in team sports without significant anxiety.

4.3. Relationship between the respondents’ sports and physical anxiety and self-actualization

The Spearman Rho correlation coefficient test revealed a correlation of (-0.271) with a p-value of (0.000), indicating a statistically significant, negative relationship between sports and physical activity anxiety and self-actualization among the respondents at an alpha level of (0.05). The negative correlation signifies that as levels of sports and physical activity anxiety increase, the tendency toward self-actualization decreases, albeit at a moderate rate. This inverse relationship suggests that higher anxiety related to sports and physical activities may hinder students’ progress in achieving self-actualization, which includes self-awareness, personal growth, and goal orientation.

This finding implies that anxiety in sports and physical activity contexts could be a psychological barrier for students, limiting their ability to pursue self-fulfillment and personal development. The presence of anxiety may prevent them from engaging fully in physical activities, potentially undermining their confidence and self-perception. This aligns with research indicating that anxiety, particularly performance-related or social evaluative anxiety, can lead to avoidance behaviors, reducing opportunities for skill development, social interaction, and the cultivation of self-efficacy—all of which are vital for self-actualization [48].

Moreover, these findings underscore the importance of addressing sports and physical activity anxiety to foster a more supportive environment that can enable students to reach their potential. By implementing strategies to alleviate sports and physical activity anxiety, institutions could facilitate more positive experiences in physical education and recreational activities, ultimately aiding students in their journey toward self-actualization. This relationship points to the broader significance of mental well-being and confidence in physical contexts as foundational for holistic development and psychological growth in university students, suggesting that reducing anxiety in these areas can play a crucial role in promoting self-actualizing behaviors and mindsets.

The findings of this study underscore the importance of addressing sports and physical activity anxiety as a pathway to supporting self-actualization among university students, offering crucial insights for both policy and practice within educational institutions. Given the observed negative correlation between sports and physical activity anxiety and self-actualization, these results suggest that higher anxiety levels may limit students' engagement and growth in physical, social, and psychological domains. This limitation not only impacts individual well-being but also represents a missed opportunity for institutions to nurture well-rounded, self-actualizing graduates.

For policymakers in education, these findings highlight the need for policies that integrate mental health support with physical education curricula. Implementing programs that reduce sports and physical activity anxiety—such as structured psychological support, anxiety management workshops, and inclusive, non-competitive activity options—can cultivate a supportive environment for students to participate without fear of judgment or failure [49], [50]. Policies could also mandate that physical education instructors receive training in mental health awareness, equipping them with the skills to recognize and address anxiety in students, which could foster more inclusive, empathetic sports programs [51].

Practically, this research suggests that educators should adopt a more individualized approach to physical education by incorporating diverse activity options that respect varying comfort levels and anxieties around sports and physical activity. Providing low-stakes, judgment-free environments, such as intramural leagues or mindfulness-oriented movement classes, could be particularly beneficial. Programs like these allow students to engage at their own pace, helping reduce the stress and social anxiety associated with performance and peer comparison [52]. Additionally, opportunities for peer support within these settings, like team-building exercises or shared reflection sessions, can help students build social connections while mitigating anxiety-related avoidance behaviors, supporting both psychological and social growth [53], [54].

Furthermore, integrating psychological and physical education aligns with broader educational goals, as physical activities that promote self-awareness, resilience, and emotional regulation are shown to support academic success and well-being [55]. This holistic approach not only addresses immediate issues of anxiety and participation but also supports long-term self-actualization by empowering students to pursue personal growth and fulfillment across multiple aspects of their lives. Ultimately, this study's findings advocate for institutional practices and policies that view physical activity not merely as a requirement but as a crucial element of personal development, helping to create an educational environment that is supportive of both mental and physical health.

5. CONCLUSION

This study highlights the importance of addressing sports and physical activity anxiety among university students, as even low levels of anxiety—particularly in socially evaluative situations—can hinder participation in physical activities. By fostering inclusive, judgment-free environments and reducing performance pressures, institutions can create spaces where students feel more comfortable engaging in exercise and sports. These efforts could contribute to improved mental and physical well-being, ultimately supporting students in maintaining an active lifestyle. Additionally, students' moderate levels of self-actualization suggest they are in the process of personal growth and self-discovery. Universities can enhance this developmental journey by promoting self-exploration and goal-setting through academic and extracurricular programs, ensuring students have access to environments that nurture resilience, adaptability, and self-fulfillment.

The negative correlation between sports and physical activity anxiety and self-actualization underscores the need to address psychological barriers that may hinder students' personal growth. Anxiety in physical activity settings may limit opportunities for self-discovery, social interaction, and overall well-being, making targeted interventions essential. Universities should integrate mental health support with physical activity programs, ensuring a holistic approach that reinforces both physical and psychological development. Future research can further explore how demographic factors influence this relationship, while longitudinal and intervention-based studies could identify effective strategies for reducing anxiety and fostering self-actualization. Expanding research to include diverse student populations will strengthen the applicability of findings, guiding policies and practices that promote well-rounded student development.

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

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Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

INFORMED CONSENT

We have obtained informed consent from all individuals included in this study.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

The research related to human use has been complied with all the relevant national regulations and institutional policies in accordance with the tenets of the Helsinki Declaration and has been approved by the authors' institutional review board or equivalent committee.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article.

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